

Comprehensive Water Quality Assessment of the Girna River in Kalwan Taluka, Nashik: Seasonal Trends and Environmental Implications

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Abstract

Current study assesses the water quality of the Girna River in Kalwan Taluka, Nashik, over a two-year period by analyzing various physical and chemical parameters. The research focuses on fluctuations in atmospheric and water temperature, pH levels, dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), total alkalinity (TA), total hardness (TH), and key nutrient concentrations. By evaluating seasonal trends across multiple stations, the study identifies potential environmental implications and offers valuable insights into the river's ecological health. The findings aim to support sustainable water resource management and conservation efforts to protect this vital water source.

Key Words: Water quality assessment, Girna River, physicochemical parameters, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, seasonal variations, pollution control, water resource management.

Introduction

Fresh water body and rivers play a crucial role in maintaining ecological balance, providing water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes (Ajith et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2023). However, increasing human activities, pollution, and climate variations impact river water quality, making periodic monitoring essential (Sharma et al., 2014; Wagay et al., 2020). The Girna River, an important tributary of the Tapi River, is a primary water source for many communities in Kalwan Taluka, Nashik. Its water quality is influenced by agricultural runoff, urban waste, and

seasonal climatic changes, necessitating an in-depth study of its physicochemical characteristics (Khan et al., 2023a; Meride and Ayenew, 2016; Yang et al., 2023, 2023). This research evaluates the biotope of the Girna River by examining key physical and chemical indicators to understand seasonal variations and possible pollution sources (Sharma and Chaudhry, 2015; Syeed et al., 2023). The study's findings will assist policymakers, environmentalists, and local communities in implementing conservation strategies and sustainable water management practices (Newton and Melaram, 2023).

Methodology

The study was conducted at six strategically selected sampling stations along the Girna River, covering diverse environmental conditions to ensure a comprehensive analysis. Data was collected over two consecutive years, with periodic sampling to capture seasonal variations in water quality. Water samples were analyzed for a range of physical and chemical parameters using standard laboratory techniques (Sharma et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2023; Zolekar et al., 2021). The collected data was compared across stations to evaluate spatial and temporal trends, helping to identify potential pollution sources and fluctuations in water quality (Jeba Sonia J et al., 2023; M. B. Patil and P. A. Khan, 2017; Sivaranjani et al., 2015). The study area, located in a semi-arid region, is characterized by agricultural land use, urban settlements, and seasonal water flow variations, all of which contribute to changes in water composition.

Results and Discussion

Physical Parameters: Atmospheric temperature exhibited seasonal fluctuations, with the highest recorded value of 33.6°C in April 2023 at GSS-VI, while the lowest temperature was 14.6°C in December 2022 at GSS-III. The average temperatures ranged between 25.62°C and 27.32°C, indicating moderate variability across different stations and seasons. Water temperature, which significantly affects aquatic life and chemical processes, showed a similar seasonal pattern (Khatri and Tyagi, 2015). The highest recorded water temperature was 29.9°C in May 2022 at GSS-V, while the lowest was 15.2°C in December 2023 at GSS-I. The data suggests that higher temperatures are observed between March and October, aligning with the region's hotter climatic conditions.

Chemical Parameters: The pH levels across all stations indicated an alkaline nature, with values consistently above 7. The highest pH value recorded was 8.9 in May 2023 at GSS-III, while the lowest was 7.1 in August 2022 at GSS-V. The second year of observation showed a slight increase in alkalinity, which may be linked to anthropogenic influences such as agricultural runoff or wastewater discharge. Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels, which are critical for aquatic life sustainability, varied throughout the study period. The highest DO concentration of 10.88 mg/L was observed in September 2022 at GSS-III, while the lowest was 5.44 mg/L in April 2022 at GSS-VI. Despite fluctuations, the average DO levels remained above 7.8 mg/L, indicating that the river maintains sufficient oxygenation for aquatic organisms (Labib et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2015; Sivaranjani et al., 2015).

Biological oxygen demand (BOD), an indicator of organic pollution, ranged between 1.2 mg/L and 5.2 mg/L. The maximum value was recorded in May 2022 at GSS-VI, while the minimum was observed in August 2022 at GSS-I, GSS-II, and GSS-V. The BOD values suggest that organic contamination is relatively low, though certain locations exhibit higher organic load due to localized pollution sources (Archana et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2023b; M. B. Patil and P. A. Khan, 2017; Sharma and Chaudhry, 2015; Syeed et al., 2023). Free carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels showed significant seasonal variation, with the highest concentration of 11.73 mg/L recorded in July 2023 at GSS-I and GSS-II. Interestingly, CO₂ was absent during the summer months, likely due to increased photosynthetic activity reducing free CO₂ availability.

Total alkalinity (TA) ranged from 120.33 mg/L to 193.33 mg/L, with the highest value recorded in May 2022 at GSS-VI. Similarly, total hardness (TH) fluctuated between 150.66 mg/L and 192 mg/L, with the highest concentration recorded in May 2023 at GSS-III. The observed increase in hardness in the second year may be attributed to geological and anthropogenic influences such as mineral leaching and agricultural runoff (Newton and Melaram, 2023; Sinha, 2023; Yang et al., 2023). Calcium and magnesium concentrations exhibited seasonal patterns, with calcium levels ranging from 23.24 mg/L to 41.41 mg/L and magnesium levels fluctuating between 15.5 mg/L and 29.23 mg/L. The data suggests that higher concentrations were observed during the summer months, possibly due to evaporation and reduced water flow leading to higher mineral concentrations.

Sulphate (SO₄) levels showed moderate fluctuations, with concentrations ranging between 1.3 mg/L and 15.3 mg/L. The highest sulphate level was recorded in July 2023 at GSS-III, which may indicate seasonal changes in runoff patterns. Similarly, phosphate (PO₄) concentrations varied between 0.03 mg/L and 1.28 mg/L, with the highest value recorded in July 2023 at GSS-III. Elevated phosphate levels suggest nutrient enrichment, likely due to agricultural fertilizers and organic waste discharge.

The following graphs illustrate the seasonal variations in key water quality parameters of the Girna River across different months of the year.

Graph 01. Seasonal variations

Graph 02. pH fluctuations

Graph 03. Dissolved Oxygen (DO) levels

Graph 04. Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

Graph 05. Total Hardness (TH) and Total Alkalinity (TA) Graph 06. Nutrient concentrations

The graph 01 shows atmospheric and water temperatures, highlighting an increase from January to June, with peaks in May and June, followed by a gradual decline. The graph 02 represents pH fluctuations, revealing a steady rise from 7.3 in January to a peak of 8.7 in July, before declining towards December. The dissolved oxygen (DO) levels decrease during warmer months (June to August) due to higher temperatures and biological activity, with the lowest values in July. In contrast, the biological oxygen demand (BOD) levels increase during these months, indicating a higher organic load and microbial decomposition (Ebrahimzadeh et al., 2021). The total hardness and alkalinity graphs indicate an increasing trend from January to July, suggesting mineral dissolution and reduced water flow during the dry season. The final graph depicts phosphate and sulphate levels, which show higher concentrations in mid-year months, likely due to agricultural runoff and organic decomposition.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that the Girna River exhibits distinct seasonal variations in its physicochemical properties. During the summer months, most parameters, including temperature, alkalinity, hardness, and phosphate levels, showed an increase, likely due to evaporation, reduced water flow, and higher anthropogenic activity. The river maintains adequate dissolved oxygen levels, suggesting a healthy aquatic ecosystem despite some localized pollution sources (Rentier and Cammeraat, 2022; Syeed et al., 2023). The observed alkalinity, hardness, and nutrient levels indicate a moderate anthropogenic influence, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and

conservation measures to maintain water quality (Bhalla et al., 2012; Sharma and Chaudhry, 2015; Sharma et al., 2014).

Regular monitoring of the Girna River is essential to detect long-term changes in water quality and prevent deterioration. Agricultural runoff should be controlled by promoting sustainable farming practices, such as buffer zones and controlled fertilizer use, to reduce phosphate accumulation. Public awareness programs should be initiated to educate local communities on sustainable water usage and the impacts of pollution. Additionally, effective water conservation policies should be implemented to safeguard water resources and maintain ecological balance in the region (23).

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